

Documentation of the FDOrganizer Metadata Schema

Introduction

In order to ensure the long-term availability of digital objects, several components must be considered. In addition to the preservation of readability, which is usually achieved through appropriate technical measures, it is also necessary to ensure the interpretability of the data. In this context, both the preservation at the logical level, which ensures the future usability of the data, and the preservation at the semantic level, which above all enables reuse in terms of content and structure, are important. In order to create the best possible conditions for the long-term availability of valuable research data, it is therefore necessary to provide them with appropriately detailed metadata.

For this purpose, a detailed generic metadata schema for the archiving of research data using the FDOrganizer¹ has been developed. The FDOrganizer is an open source tool² that enables researchers to prepare their research data for the long-term availability and enhance it with the necessary metadata. The metadata schema that has been implemented for the tool is based on version 4.6 of the DataCite metadata schema³, in order to ensure a broad reusability and compatibility of the metadata.

This documentation provides an overview of the individual metadata fields and their usage.

Overview

In the interest of long-term availability, some of the fields are mandatory in order to ensure findability and a minimum of interpretability. For this purpose, six of the elements have been declared as mandatory fields.

The other fields are optional fields and may be filled in depending on their occurrence, but their specification is not mandatory.

In general, however, the metadata should be described in as much detail as possible, as this may enable or facilitate future reuse.

¹ <https://lzv-bayern.de/langzeitverfügbarkeit/fdorganizer>

² Code for the FDOrganizer: <https://gitlab.lzv-bayern.de/forschungsdaten>

³ <https://schema.datacite.org/> in the current version 4.6

Mandatory fields

Property	Occurrence
Identifier	1-n
Creator	1-n
Title	1-n
Publishing	1
ResourceType	1
Description	1-n

Optional fields**Content**

Property	Occurrence
Subject & Keywords	0-n
Date	0-n
Language	0-n
Version	0-1

Data Scope

Property	Occurrence
Size	0-n
Geolocation	0-1
Timeframe	0-n

Data Creation & Acquisition

Property	Occurrence
Contributor	0-n
Funding	0-n
Datasource	0-n
Software	0-n

Related Documents

Property	Occurrence
Related Works	0-n

Usage & Rights

Property	Occurrence
Rights	0-1

Detail information

The following table defines the properties of the metadata schema and provides an overview of the allowed values, examples and constraints of the respective property. The column Occurrence (Occ.) indicates how often the corresponding property can occur. The condition column specifies the conditions under which the corresponding property can occur. In order to make the following documentation easier to read, inside the table the **parent properties** are highlighted in color.

0-n = optional, may be repeated as often as required

0-1 = optional, not repeatable

1-n = obligatory, may be repeated as often as required

1 = obligatory, not repeatable

Mandatory fields

Property	Occ.	Definition	Allowed values, examples, constraints	Conditions
Identifier	1-n	Persistent identifier that uniquely identifies the resource		
resourceIdentifierScheme	1	Type of the identifier	Values: - DOI (Digital Object Identifier) - URI (Uniform Resource Identifier) - Other	
resourceIdentifierUri	1	Unique URI identifier of the resource	Format of the URI should be "https://example.com/dataset".	Only used if <i>resourceIdentifierScheme</i> is "URI".
resourceIdentifierDoi	1	Unique DOI identifier of the resource	Format of the DOI should be "10.1109/example".	Only used if <i>resourceIdentifierScheme</i> is "DOI".
resourceIdentifierName	1	Name of the custom identifier	Free text.	Only used if <i>resourceIdentifierScheme</i> is "Other".
resourceIdentifier	1	Unique custom identifier of the resource	Free text.	Only used if <i>resourceIdentifierScheme</i> is "Other".
Creator	1-n	Main researcher or organization that is responsible for the data	May be the researcher involved in producing the data or authors of a publication. Multiple creators are possible.	
creatorType	1	Type of the creator	Values: - Person - Organization	
organisationIdentifierType	1	Type of the organizational identifier	Values: - ROR (Research Organization Registry) - Name - GND (Gemeinsame Normdatei)	Only used if <i>creatorType</i> is "Organization".

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Property	Occ.	Definition	Allowed values, examples, constraints	Conditions
organizationROR	0-1	Unique ROR identifier of the organization	Format of ROR identifier should be: "01eezs655".	Only used if: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>creatorType</i> is "Organization" - <i>organisationIdentifierType</i> is "ROR"
organizationGND	0-1	Unique GND identifier of the organization	Format of the GND should be: "1012048-8".	Only used if: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>creatorType</i> is "Organization" - <i>organisationIdentifierType</i> is "GND"
organizationName	0-1	Name of the organization	Free text.	Only used if <i>creatorType</i> is "Organization".
personIdentifierType	1	Type of the personal identifier	Values: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Name - ORCID (Open Researcher and Contributor ID) 	Only used if <i>creatorType</i> is "Person".
creatorFirstName	0-1	Personal or first name of the creator	Free text.	Only used if: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>creatorType</i> is "Person" - <i>personIdentifierType</i> is "Name"
creatorLastName	0-1	Surname or last name of the creator	Free text.	Only used if: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>creatorType</i> is "Person" - <i>personIdentifierType</i> is "Name"
creatorOrcid	1	Unique ORCID identifier of the creator	Format of ORCID should be: "0000-0001-2345-6789".	Only used if: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>creatorType</i> is "Person" - <i>personIdentifierType</i> is "ORCID"
creatorAffiliationIdentifierType	1	Type of identifier of the creator's affiliation	Values: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - ROR - Name - GND 	Only used if <i>creatorType</i> is "Person".

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Property	Occ.	Definition	Allowed values, examples, constraints	Conditions
creatorAffiliationName	0-1	Name of the creator's organizational or institutional affiliation	Free text.	Only used if: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>creatorType</i> is "Person" - <i>creatorAffiliationIdentifierType</i> is "Name"
creatorAffiliationROR	0-1	Unique ROR identifier of the creator's affiliated organization	Format of ROR identifier should be: "01eezs655".	Only used if: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>creatorType</i> is "Person" - <i>creatorAffiliationIdentifierType</i> is "ROR"
creatorAffiliationGND	0-1	Unique GND identifier of the creator's affiliated organization	Format of the GND should be: "1012048-8".	Only used if: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>creatorType</i> is "Person" - <i>creatorAffiliationIdentifierType</i> is "GND"
Title	1-n	Title or name by which the resource is known		
titleType	1	Type of the title	Values: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Main title - Subtitle - Alternative title - Other 	
titleText	1	Title	Free text.	
Publishing	1	Indicates whether a resource has been published and records additional information about the publishing		
isPublished	1	Whether the resource is published or not	Values: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Yes - No 	

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Property	Occ.	Definition	Allowed values, examples, constraints	Conditions
publisher	0-n	Entity that holds, archives, publishes, prints, distributes, releases, issues or produces the resource		Only used if <i>isPublished</i> is "Yes".
publisherIdentifierScheme	1	Type of the identifier	Values: - ORCID - ROR - Name	Only used if <i>isPublished</i> is "Yes".
publisherOrcid	0-1	Unique ORCID identifier of the publisher	Format of ORCID should be: "0000-0001-2345-6789".	Only used if: - <i>isPublished</i> is "Yes" - <i>publisherIdentifierScheme</i> is "ORCID"
publisherRor	0-1	Unique ROR identifier of the publisher	Format of ROR identifier should be: "01eezs655".	Only used if: - <i>isPublished</i> is "Yes" - <i>publisherIdentifierScheme</i> is "ROR"
publisherName	0-1	Full name of the publisher	Free text.	Only used if: - <i>isPublished</i> is "Yes" - <i>publisherIdentifierScheme</i> is "Name"
publicationDate	0-1	Date of publication	Format: DD/MM/YYYY	Only used if <i>isPublished</i> is "Yes".
ResourceType	1	Description of the resource		
resourceTypeGeneral	1	The general object type of the resource	Values: - Audiovisual - Book - Book chapter - Collection - Computational notebook - Conference paper	

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Property	Occ.	Definition	Allowed values, examples, constraints	Conditions
			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Conference proceeding - Data paper - Dataset - Dissertation - Event - Image - Interactive resource - Journal - Journal article - Model - Output management plan - Peer review - Physical object - Preprint - Report - Service - Software - Sound - Standard - Text - Workflow - Other 	
Description	1-n	Additional information for describing the resource		
descriptionType	1	Type of description	Values: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Abstract - Table of Contents - Readme - Other 	
textAbstract	0-1	Abstract of the resource	Free text.	Only used if <i>descriptionType</i> is "Abstract".
textTOC	0-1	Table of contents of the resource	Free text.	Only used if <i>descriptionType</i> is "Table of Contents".

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Property	Occ.	Definition	Allowed values, examples, constraints	Conditions
textReadme	0-1	Readme of the resource	Free text.	Only used if <i>descriptionType</i> is "Readme".
textCustom	0-1	Further content description of the resource	Free text.	Only used if <i>descriptionType</i> is "Other".

Optional fields

Content				
Property	Occ.	Definition	Allowed values, examples, constraints	Conditions
Subject	0-n	Classification or keyword describing the resource		
subjectIdentifierType	1	Type of the identifier	Values: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - DDC (Dewey Decimal Classification) - GND - Wikidata - Keyword list 	
subjectIdentifierDdc	0-1	DDC classification code for the subject	Format of the DDC code should be: "551.6".	Only used if <i>subjectIdentifierType</i> is "DDC".
subjectIdentifierGND	0-1	GND classification code for the subject	Format of the GND should be: "4031178-8".	Only used if <i>subjectIdentifierType</i> is "GND".
subjectIdentifierWikidata	0-1	Wikidata identifier for the subject	Format of the Wikidata identifier should be: "Q52139".	Only used if <i>subjectIdentifierType</i> is "Wikidata".
subjectIdentifierCSV	0-1	List of keywords for describing the resource	For example: "psychology, cognitive bias, survey".	Only used if <i>subjectIdentifierType</i> is "Keyword list".
Date	0-n	Dates relevant to the resource		
dateType	1	Type of date	Values: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Accepted - Available - Copyrighted - Collected - Created - Issued 	

Content				
Property	Occ.	Definition	Allowed values, examples, constraints	Conditions
			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Submitted - Updated - Valid - Withdrawn - Other 	
dateInformation	0-1	Specification of the date	Specification in the format: DD/MM/YYYY	
Language	0-n	Primary natural or programming language of the resource		
languageType	1	Type of language	Values: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Natural language - Programming language 	
languageCode	0-1	Specification of the language used for the resource	Values: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - English - Deutsch - Francais - Other 	Only used if <i>languageType</i> is "Natural language".
customLanguage	0-1	Specification of the custom language used for the resource	Free text.	Only used if: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>languageType</i> is "Natural language" - <i>languageCode</i> is "Other"
customProgramming-Language	0-1	Specification of the custom programming language used for the resource	Example: Python, Java, R, ...	Only used if <i>languageType</i> is "Programming language".
Version	0-1	Version number of the resource	Format should be: majorversion.minorversion. Example: 1.2	

Data Scope				
Property	Occ.	Definition	Allowed values, examples, constraints	Conditions
Size	0-n	Size or duration of the resource	Specification of the size (bytes, pages,...) or the duration (minutes, hours,...). Free text. Example: 12 pages, 8 MB,...	
Geolocation	0-1	Geographical location or area where the data was collected or about which the data is focused		
geolocationType	1	Type of the geolocation	Value: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Place name - Point - Polygon 	
geoLocationPlace	0-1	Name of a geographic location	Free text.	Only used if <i>geolocationType</i> is "Place name".
geoLocationPointLatitude	1	Latitudinal dimension of a geographical point location	The latitude should be expressed in decimal degrees. Per definition, the latitude is settled in the area of ± 90 degrees. Example: 49.926789	Only used if <i>geolocationType</i> is "Point".
geoLocationPointLongitude	1	Longitudinal dimension of a geographical point location	The longitude should be expressed in decimal degrees. Per definition, the longitude is settled in the area of ± 180 degrees. Example: 11.586352	Only used if <i>geolocationType</i> is "Point".
geoLocationPolygonPoint	4-n	Polygon area of a geographical area, defined by a set of points	Each polygon point consists of latitude and longitude. There must be at least 4 non-aligned points to make a closed curve. The last point should be the same as the first.	Only used if <i>geolocationType</i> is "Polygon".

Data Scope				
Property	Occ.	Definition	Allowed values, examples, constraints	Conditions
geoLocationPolygonLongitude	1	Longitudinal dimension of a polygon point location	The longitude should be expressed in decimal degrees. Per definition, the longitude is settled in the area of ± 180 degrees. Example: 11.580483	Only used if <i>geolocationType</i> is "Polygon".
geoLocationPolygonLatitude	1	Latitudinal dimension of a polygon point location	The latitude should be expressed in decimal degrees. Per definition, the latitude is settled in the area of ± 90 degrees. Example: 48.148213	Only used if <i>geolocationType</i> is "Polygon".
Timeframe	0-n	Information about the temporal properties or the temporal topic of the resource		
timeframeType	1	Type of timeframe	Values: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Point in time - Time range - Historical event 	
timeframePoint	0-1	Specification of a point in time	Format should be: DD/MM/YYYY	Only used if <i>timeframeType</i> is "Point in time".
timeframeRangeStart	0-1	Starting point for the specification of a range of time	Format should be: DD/MM/YYYY	Only used if <i>timeframeType</i> is "Time range".
timeframeRangeEnd	0-1	End point for the specification of a range of time	Format should be: DD/MM/YYYY	Only used if <i>timeframeType</i> is "Time range".
timeframeEvent	0-1	Specification of a historical event	Name of a historically unambiguous, temporally defined event. Free text.	Only used if <i>timeframeType</i> is "Historical event".

Data Creation & Acquisition				
Property	Occ.	Definition	Allowed values, examples, constraints	Conditions
Contributor	0-n	Person or institution contributing to the creation or development of the resource	Multiple contributors are possible.	
contributorType	1	Type of contributor	Values: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Person - Organization 	
personalContributorRole	1	Role of the personal contributor	Values: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Contact Person - Data Collector - Data Curator - Data Manager - Editor - Producer - Project Leader - Project Manager - Project Member - Related Person - Researcher - Rights Holder - Sponsor - Supervisor - Work Package Leader 	Only used if <i>contributorType</i> is "Person".
organizationalContributor-Role	1	Role of the organizational contributor	Values: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Distributor - Editor - Hosting Institution - Producer - Research Group - Rights Holder - Sponsor 	Only used if <i>contributorType</i> is "Organization".

Data Creation & Acquisition				
Property	Occ.	Definition	Allowed values, examples, constraints	Conditions
organizationalContributorIdentifierType	1	Type of organizational identifier	Values: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - ROR - Name - GND 	Only used if <i>contributorType</i> is "Organization".
organizationalContributorROR	1	Unique ROR identifier of the organization	Format of ROR identifier should be: "01eezs655".	Only used if: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>contributorType</i> is "Organization" - <i>organizationalContributorIdentifierType</i> is "ROR"
organizationName	1	Name of the organization	Free text.	Only used if: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>contributorType</i> is "Organization" - <i>organizationalContributorIdentifierType</i> is "Name"
organizationGND	1	Unique GND identifier of the organization	Format of the GND should be: "1012048-8".	Only used if: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>contributorType</i> is "Organization" - <i>organizationalContributorIdentifierType</i> is "GND"
personalContributorIdentifierType	1	Type of personal identifier	Values: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Name - ORCID 	Only used if <i>contributorType</i> is "Person".
personalContributorLastName	1	Surname or last name of the contributor	Free text.	Only used if: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>contributorType</i> is "Person" - <i>personalContributorIdentifierType</i> is "Name"
personalContributorFirstName	1	Personal or first name of the contributor	Free text.	Only used if: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>contributorType</i> is "Person" - <i>personalContributorIdentifierType</i> is "Name"

Data Creation & Acquisition				
Property	Occ.	Definition	Allowed values, examples, constraints	Conditions
personalContributorOrcid	1	Unique ORCID identifier of the contributor	Format of ORCID should be: "0000-0001-2345-6789".	Only used if: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>contributorType</i> is "Person" - <i>personalContributorIdentifierType</i> is "ORCID"
personalContributorAffiliationIdentifierType	1	Type of identifier of the contributor's affiliation	Values: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - ROR - GND - Name 	Only used if <i>contributorType</i> is "Person".
personalContributorAffiliationROR	0-1	Unique ROR identifier of the contributor's affiliated organization	Format of ROR identifier should be: "01eezs655".	Only used if: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>contributorType</i> is "Person" - <i>personalContributorAffiliationIdentifierType</i> is "ROR"
personalContributorAffiliationGND	0-1	Unique GND identifier of the contributor's affiliated organization	Format of the GND should be: "1012048-8".	Only used if: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>contributorType</i> is "Person" - <i>personalContributorAffiliationIdentifierType</i> is "GND"
personalContributorAffiliationName	0-1	Name of the contributor's organizational or institutional affiliation	Free text.	Only used if: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>contributorType</i> is "Person" - <i>personalContributorAffiliationIdentifierType</i> is "Name"
Funding	0-n	Information about research funding	Information on financial support or fundings.	
funderIdentifierType	1	Type of the identifier	Values: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Crossref Funder ID - ROR - Name 	

Data Creation & Acquisition				
Property	Occ.	Definition	Allowed values, examples, constraints	Conditions
funderCrossref	1	Unique Crossref identifier of the funder	Format of Crossref ID should be: "doi.org/10.13039/501100001659".	Only used if <i>funderIdentifierType</i> is "Crossref Funder ID".
funderROR	1	Unique ROR identifier of the funder	Format of ROR identifier should be: "018mejw64".	Only used if <i>funderIdentifierType</i> is "ROR".
funderName	1	Name of funding provider	Free text. Example: DFG, BMBF, ...	Only used if <i>funderIdentifierType</i> is "Name".
award	0-n	Information about the award of the funding		
awardTitle	0-1	Title of the award or project	Free text. Example: Forschungsdatendienst für die Ost-, Ostmittel- und Südosteuropaforschung (OstData)	
awardNumber	0-1	Code of the award or project assigned by the funder	Example: "413708228"	
awardURI	0-1	URI leading to a page with further information about the funding	Example: " https://gepris.dfg.de/gepris/projekt/413708228 "	
Datasource	0-n	Information about the data source		
dataSourceDetail	1	Type or category of the data source	Values: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Instrument - Media - Observation - Trial - Survey - Organism - Other 	

Data Creation & Acquisition				
Property	Occ.	Definition	Allowed values, examples, constraints	Conditions
customDataSourceType	1	Specification of the custom type	Free text.	Only used if <i>dataSourceDetail</i> is "Other".
Software	0-n	Information about the used software		
softwareType	1	Type of software use	Values: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Resource production - Resource processing - Resource viewing - Other 	
customSoftwareType	1	Specification of the custom type	Free text.	Only used if <i>softwareType</i> is "Other".
softwareName	1	Name of used software	Free text.	
softwareVersion	1	Version of used software	For specification, a major and minor version number is recommended.	
softwareAdditional	0-1	Further information about the used software	Free text. Specification of the software, for example if open source software was used.	

Related Documents				
Property	Occ.	Definition	Allowed values, examples, constraints	Conditions
Related works	0-n	Information about a related resource and their relationship		
relationType	1	Type of relationship between the resource (A) and the related resource (B)	Values: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - is cited by - is supplement to - is continued by - continues - is new version of - is part of - is published in - is referenced by - is identical to - is derived from - is source of 	
relationIdentifierScheme	1	Type of identifier of the related resource	Values: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - DOI - URI - Other 	
relationURI	0-1	Unique URI identifier of the related resource	Format of the URI should be "https://example.com/dataset".	Only used if <i>relationIdentifierScheme</i> is "URI".
relationDoi	0-1	Unique DOI identifier of the related resource	Format of the DOI should be "10.1109/example".	Only used if <i>relationIdentifierScheme</i> is "DOI".
relationIdentifier	0-1	Unique custom identifier of the related resource	Free text.	Only used if <i>relationIdentifierScheme</i> is "Other".

Usage & Rights				
Property	Occ.	Definition	Allowed values, examples, constraints	Conditions
Rights	0-1	Rights information for the resource.		
rightsType	1	Type of license or rights in general	Values: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Creative Commons License - GNU General Public License - Apache License - All rights reserved - Other 	
rightsIdentifierCC	1	Type of Creative Commons license of the resource	Example: CC-BY-4.0	Only used if <i>rightsType</i> is “Creative Commons License”.
rightsURICC	0-1	URI of the used Creative Commons license	Example: https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/	Only used if <i>rightsType</i> is “Creative Commons License”.
rightsIdentifierGNU	1	Type of GNU license of the resource	Example: GPL-3.0-or-later	Only used if <i>rightsType</i> is “GNU General Public License”.
rightsURIGNU	0-1	URI of the used GNU license	Example: https://www.gnu.org/licenses/gpl-3.0.txt	Only used if <i>rightsType</i> is “GNU General Public License”.
rightsIdentifierApache	1	Type of Apache license of the resource	Example: Apache-2.0	Only used if <i>rightsType</i> is “Apache License”.
rightsURIApache	0-1	URI of the used Apache license	Example: https://www.apache.org/licenses/LICENSE-2.0	Only used if <i>rightsType</i> is “Apache License”.
rightsIdentifierCustomType	1	Specification of the custom type of the rights or license	Free text. Additional information about the custom rights or license type. For example, if it's a software license.	Only used if <i>rightsType</i> is “Other”.

Usage & Rights				
Property	Occ.	Definition	Allowed values, examples, constraints	Conditions
rightsIdentifierCustom	1	Short, standardized name of the custom license	Free text: For example: MIT License	Only used if <i>rightsType</i> is "Other".
rightsURICustom	0-1	URI of the custom rights or license	Example: https://opensource.org/licenses/mit	Only used if <i>rightsType</i> is "Other"

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